

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE DATA OF VARIOUS CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents test methods for measuring the interlaminar energy release rate (fracture toughness) under mode I and mode II loading conditions. Both methods are presently under discussion in the European Group of Fracture (EGF) to become standard testing procedures. Various data were already obtained on different systems including thermosetting and thermoplastic matrix composites, reinforced with unidirectional fibers or woven fabrics. Besides a comparison of the interlaminar fracture toughness data as a function of material composition, effects of the specimens' stiffness, width and thickness, of the starter crack dimensions, and of different data reduction methods are discussed. SEM investigations of the interlaminar fracture surfaces were made to describe possible micro-failure mechanisms. Finally methods to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness are presented.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Polymer; Energy Release Rate; Mode I; Mode II

1. INTRODUCTION

A unidirectional continuous fiber reinforcement in high performance composite materials leads to high specific strength and stiffness in fiber direction but very low properties transverse to it. Usually laminates made of plies with different fiber orientation or of plies with woven fabric fiber reinforcement are used in structures to overcome this problem in two dimensions. A critical failure mode of these laminates is, however, still existing in form of delaminations or interlaminar fracture due to loads in the third dimension.

A lot of investigations have been published so far dealing with the measurement of the critical energy to cause delamination in order to characterize new materials in means of this property, to study fiber and matrix behaviour or to predict the damage tolerance. However, most of these

studies were carried out using different specimen geometries, test procedures or data reduction methods so that a comparison of the values obtained is questionable.

Therefore, the European Group of Fracture (EGF) started a program in which fundamental problems for standardization, such as effects of the specimens' stiffness, width and thickness, of the starter crack dimensions, of the test rate and of different data reduction methods on interlaminar fracture toughness values in mode I (G_{Ic}) and mode II (G_{IIc}) loading conditions are investigated. The final objective was to establish a unified standard testing procedure. The present status is a joint Round Robin exercise of the EGF together with the ASTM group D30.02.02 and the Japanese Industrial Standards group, involving some fifty academic or industrial participants.

Besides the Round Robin exercises, the authors performed additional investigations, using the current standard test procedure, and the results are also described in this paper.

2. INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TESTING AND DATA REDUCTION

2.1 Mode I The crack opening mode I loading condition is realized using the parallel-sided DCB (double cantilever beam) specimen geometry (Fig. 1). In order to initiate delamination a foil of $a = 50$ mm length is placed at one end and mid-thickness of the laminate. The load (P) is introduced via either hinges or machined loading blocks. The specimen is loaded continuously in displacement control. The crosshead rate should be 1 mm/min. Load and displacement (u) are recorded throughout the test. The initial crack length is measured on the specimen edge with the help of a layer of white ink and then crack propagation is noted every 5 mm (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1: DCB test geometry

Fig. 2: Load-displacement diagram

From each test several values for G_{Ic} may be calculated from the recorded data sets (a , P , u). Crack initiation may be determined from the load and displacement at the point of deviation from linearity (point a_0 , Fig. 2). Because this point may be hard to define other possibilities for the determination of the initiation value are under discussion and part of the current standard protocol [1]. For each crack length measured during crack propagation a value of G_{Ic} may be determined.

Based on the Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM), many methods for the data analysis and calculation of G_{Ic} have been proposed [2, 3]:

Beam theory

The simple beam theory expression for the compliance of a perfectly built-in DCB specimen results in the following equation for G_{Ic} :

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3 P u}{2 w a} \quad (1)$$

Corrected beam theory

In practise, expression (1) will underestimate the compliance as the beam is not perfectly built-in. A means of correcting for the effect of crack tip rotation and shear deformation is to treat the beam as containing a slightly longer crack ($a+\Delta$). Δ may be found experimentally as the intercept on the x-axis by plotting the cube root of the compliance ($C = u/P$) as a function of crack length. G_{Ic} is then given by:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3 P u}{2 w (a+\Delta)} \quad (2)$$

Experimental compliance method

An alternative approach is to plot the compliance versus crack length on a double logarithmic plot ($C = u/P \sim a^n$). The slope of this plot (n) can be used to give G_{Ic} as follows:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{n P u}{2 w a} \quad (3)$$

2.2 Mode II Two test methods are employed to realize the inplane shear mode II loading condition: the ENF (end notched flexure) and the ELS (end loaded split) test (Fig. 3). The distance between supports ($2L$) is recommended to be 100 mm for the ENF specimen, while for the ELS specimen a free length (L) of 100 mm is suggested. The test procedures are nearly the same as in mode I testing, and further details are described elsewhere [1, 3].

Fig. 3: ENF and ELS test geometry

Due to the unstable crack propagation in the ENF specimen only one initiation value for G_{IIc} can be calculated which depends on the kind of pre-crack, either a foil, a mode I, or a shear pre-crack. The stable crack propagation in the ELS specimen allows to calculate also propagation values of G_{IIc} .

The simple beam theory expressions for G_{IIc} are:

*see
Ref. 4*

$$\text{ENF:} \quad G_{IIc} = \frac{9 a^2 P u}{2 w (2 L^3 + 3 a^3)} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{ELS:} \quad G_{IIc} = \frac{9 a^2 P u}{2 w (L^3 + 3 a^3)} \quad (5)$$

Corrections for large displacement and transverse shear are suggested and already described elsewhere [1, 3, 4]. Alternatively an experimental compliance calibration can be conducted similar as described for mode I testing:

$$C = C_0 + m a^3 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and} \quad G_{IIc} = \frac{3 P^2 m a^2}{2 w} \quad (7)$$

3. RESULTS

3.1 Effects of the data reduction method A full R-curve is shown in Figure 4 generated from data of a unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced epoxy laminate (CF-EP). The initiation value for G_{Ic} (at $a = 55$ mm) is much smaller than the propagation values which finally reach a saturation. Excluding the first 10 mm of crack growth, a mean value representing the propagation value for G_{Ic} is obtained. The R-curve effect results from the increasing number of fibers bridging the crack and possible formation of side cracks in the damage zone with

increasing crack length (Fig. 5). These failure mechanisms are absent at crack initiation due to a matrix rich area ahead of the foil as it is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 4: G_{Ic} versus crack length for different data reduction methods

Fig. 5: Schematic of failure mechanisms

Fig. 6: Matrix rich area ahead of the foil pre-crack

A comparison of the G_{Ic} values for propagation obtained by the simple beam theory ($G_{Ic} = 190 \text{ J/m}^2$), the experimental compliance calibration ($G_{Ic} = 168 \text{ J/m}^2$) and the delta correction in crack length ($G_{Ic} = 165 \text{ J/m}^2$) leads generally to smaller G_{Ic} values for the latter two data reduction methods. The two experimental correction methods show similar results, especially at longer crack lengths and both methods are recommended in the standard.

3.2 Effects of the specimen dimensions One Round Robin exercise was carried out also to examine the influence of the specimen thickness. Mean propagation values for CF-EP laminates are reasonably constant for the three specimen thicknesses of 12, 24 and 40 plies (appr. 1.6, 3.2 and 5.2 mm). Using a tougher matrix like PEEK an increase of G_{Ic} by 25 % with increasing thickness (from 1.6 to 5.2 mm) can be recognized (Fig. 7). The reason is due to

increased multiple cracking (side cracks) and fiber bridging in stiffer specimens. The same tendency is observed in mode II. But the reason is not as clear as in mode I, because crack propagation was started from a mode I precrack, i.e. multiple cracks were present in thicker specimens causing multiple mode II cracks.

Fig. 7: Effects of the specimen thickness

No effect was recognized by varying the specimen width from 10 to 20 mm. However, to minimize edge effects a specimen width of 20 mm is recommended.

3.3 Effects of the starter film In Figure 8 initiation values obtained from different starter foil thicknesses and precracks for a CF-EP laminate are compared. For mode I loading conditions a thin foil results in lower G_{IC} values with less scatter. The reason is that thicker foils cause crack tip blunting which considerably rises the G_{IC} value. Mode I pre-cracking results in values similar to those obtained during propagation due to the formation of fiber bridges, but the mode II precracking gives a value close to that of the thinnest foil. It is recommended to use thin foils but care must be taken that this foil keeps straight during molding. Ply waviness results in much higher G_{IC} values because of interlaminar fiber nesting and, therefore, an increase of fiber bridges. For mode II loading conditions a short mode I pre-crack gave the best results in this study. Alternatively, a shear pre-crack can be used, which is one objective of the present Round Robin exercise.

Fig. 8: Effects of different starter cracks in CF-EP

3.4 Effects of the matrix In several studies an increase of the interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates with increasing toughness of the polymer used as the matrix is reported [3, 5]. Also the values for G_c reported in this study show the same tendency. The reason is a more pronounced plastic deformation during crack growth in tough matrices as it is indicated in Figure 9. This results in a bigger damage zone size ahead of the crack tip in tough matrices, including more energy absorption by matrix deformation, fiber-matrix debonding and fiber breakage. However, from Figure 10 it is obvious that the toughness transfer from the neat polymer to the composite is very good in case of brittle matrices but very poor in the case of tougher polymers. The low efficiency for ductile matrices is the result of the strong restrictions in the formation of a large plastic zone due to the rigid fibers. Nevertheless it still can spread over several fiber layers adjacent to the crack tip [3]. Thus such a matrix becomes still more efficient in absorbing energy by plastic deformation and fracture than a very brittle one. In a brittle matrix, only a rather small damage zone can develop before final fracture occurs with or without the presence of fibers. As, however, in the composite fiber related energy absorbing mechanisms take place too, the corresponding G_c value is greater than the one for the neat brittle matrix.

Fig. 9: Interlaminar fracture surfaces of CF-EP and CF-PEEK in mode I and mode II

Fig. 10: Efficiency of the toughness of neat polymers in composite laminates [5]

3.5 Effect of the fiber reinforcement In Figure 11 the effects of different fiber reinforcements in a brittle (EP) and a tough matrix (PEI) are compared. A unidirectional CF reinforcement in an EP-matrix results in comparison to a woven fabric CF reinforcement in much lower values for G_{IC} and G_{IIc} . This is due to the inhomogeneity and waviness of the fabric reinforcement which causes a more complex failure and a rougher fracture surface profile. Thus the surface per unit crack length becomes larger in fabric reinforced composites. In mode II the effect is more pronounced because the interlocking of the woven fabric structure increases the resistance against shear failure.

Fig. 11: Effects of the reinforcement

While the CF reinforcement results in slightly lower G_{IC} values, it reflects higher G_{IIc} values than the AF reinforcement. This may be because in mode I loading conditions the flexural properties of the fibers are more important than in mode II, where the inplane tensile and compression properties of the fibers become effective. Thus the measured results reflect the different properties of CF and AF in these two loading conditions. Also the fiber/matrix bonding is responsible for different interlaminar fracture toughnesses measured. Usually lower fiber/matrix bonding results in higher values for G_c [3].

3.6 Methods to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness Most efforts to increase the interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates were done by using tougher matrices, i.e. toughened thermosetting resins or thermoplastics. The results described above show that G_C values can be increased by 10 times but the toughness transfer from the neat polymer to the composite is restricted by the presence of the fibers. Reducing the fiber content increases the toughness but decreases the inplane properties. Toughened thermosets with reduced crosslinks reduce also the hot/wet properties of the laminate. The disadvantages of the use of thermoplastic matrices are the high costs of high temperature resistant thermoplastics and the difficulties in manufacturing, i.e. impregnation of the fibers with the relatively high viscous thermoplastic melt.

Interleaving of the laminate plies with layers of a tough neat resin can increase the interlaminar fracture toughness without decreasing the inplane properties but at the cost of a substantial increase in weight. Therefore selective toughening by interleaving the laminate only at critical points of the structure is one way to save weight. However, this method cannot be used in structures exposed to impacts all over the structure.

A third method is the use of 3D fabric composites. The orthogonal interlocking of the laminate plies by reinforcing fibers have demonstrated improved damage tolerance, impact resistance and interlaminar fracture toughness [6]. The drawback of this method is the difficult and expensive manufacturing technique by braiding, weaving or stitching. One other technique is the use of 2.5D fabrics [7]. A 3D fabric is woven with pile threads connecting the top and bottom of a 2D fabric. In a second step these piles were cut, impregnated with an epoxy resin and laminated using the usual autoclave technique. The remaining fiber piles increase the interlaminar crack growth resistance.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion the following table of interlaminar fracture toughness values can be reported:

Material	Manufacturing Method	G_{Ic} [J/m ²]		G_{IIc} [J/m ²]
		initiation	propagation	
CF (UD) - EP	Prepreg / Autoclave	115	203	528 (ENF) 730 (ELS)
CF (Fabric) - EP	Filmstacking	-	640	4970 (ELS)
CF (UD) - PEEK	Tape / Heat Press	1406	1707	2033 (ENF) 2566 (ELS)
CF (Fabric) - PEEK	Filmstacking	-	1700	5830 (ELS)
CF (UD) - PES	Tape / Heat Press	1130	2200	1850 (ENF)
CF (UD) - PA 6.6	Tape / Heat Press	-	1700	-
CF (Fabric) - PEI	Filmstacking	-	2530	6400 (ELS)
GF (UD) - PA 12	FIT / Heat Press	-	1400	1900 (ELS)
GF (UD) - PP	Tape / Welded	-	1200	-
AF (Fabric) - EP	Filmstacking	-	1010	3490 (ELS)
AF (Fabric) - PEI	Filmstacking	-	2430	4950 (ELS)

The given data are mean values of at least 4 specimens tested (in most cases much more) and the scatter is always (with the exception of CF(UD)-PES) less than 10 %. In the case of CF(UD)-PES a pronounced ply waviness leads to the high G_{Ic} value measured and a bigger scatter.

This paper showed that there are still some problems to be solved before establishing a standard test method. However, the collaboration and collection of world wide investigations is one step in this direction.

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